

CORRUPTION IN CUSTOMS AS A CHALLENGE TO NATIONAL SECURITY IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

Fatime Demiroska

catch-me2008@hotmail.com

Abstract

Corruption within the Customs Administration represents a significant threat to the national security of the Republic of North Macedonia, as it undermines economic stability, facilitates illegal trade, and erodes public trust. This study aims to examine the roots and consequences of corruption within the Customs Administration in the Republic of North Macedonia, with a particular focus on its impact on national security.

Methods: The research employs a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, including analyses of official reports, surveys, expert interviews, and review of relevant literature. Additionally, a multidimensional approach based on the Balanced Scorecard and key performance indicators (KPIs) is applied to evaluate institutional effectiveness.

Results: The findings indicate that systemic issues such as low salaries, insufficient oversight, and political interference contribute significantly to corrupt practices. These factors directly undermine institutional credibility and economic security.

Discussion: Corruption in customs creates favorable conditions for organized crime, weakens economic security, and poses a direct threat to national security. The study recommends a range of measures, including institutional reforms, increased transparency, digitalization, ethical training for personnel, whistleblower protection, and the engagement of civil society, in order to reduce corruption and strengthen national resilience.

Keywords: corruption, customs, national security, Republic of North Macedonia, institutional reforms.

1. INTRODUCTION

Systemic corruption poses a direct threat to the functioning of key state institutions, weakening the rule of law and undermining the capacity of the state to deliver fair, transparent, and effective governance (Labović,2022). This threat is particularly severe when corruption is present in institutions responsible for law enforcement and the management of public resource.

One such critical institution is the Customs Administration, which plays a central role in regulating cross-border trade, protecting state borders, and collecting revenues for the national budget. Corruption within customs services can lead to serious consequences, including economic instability, the expansion of the shadow economy, a decline in public trust in institutions, and the facilitation of transnational crime (UNODC, 2022; Transparency International, 2023).

In the context of the Republic of North Macedonia, this issue is of particular significance. As a country with a strategic geographical location in the Balkans and a transit point for numerous international trade and migration routes, the effective and honest functioning of customs authorities is essential. However, multiple reports and studies indicate that corruption within the customs system remains a persistent problem, undermining the rule of law, deterring foreign investment, and fostering organized crime.

Beyond its economic implications, corruption in customs services also carries serious security dimensions. Through bribery, document manipulation, or the concealment of illegal activities, customs officials may knowingly or unknowingly contribute to the trafficking of drugs, weapons, people, and other illicit goods. Consequently, weaknesses within the customs system can be directly linked to broader issues of national and regional security.

The aim of this study is to investigate the occurrence of corruption within the Customs Administration of the Republic of North Macedonia by analyzing its scope, the factors driving it, and the consequences it produces, with a particular emphasis on its impact on national security. The research is based on data obtained from relevant institutions, policy analyses, academic literature, and primary sources, providing a comprehensive and objective insight into the problem and offering concrete, applicable recommendations for its mitigation.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Definition of Corruption

Corruption is one of the most complex and widespread phenomena in contemporary society, referring to the misuse of public or entrusted power for personal or group gain, contrary to the public interest and legal regulations (Transparency International, 2023). In both theory and practice, corruption is defined as a phenomenon encompassing various forms and manifestations, such as bribery, favoritism, abuse of official position, conflicts of interest, and misuse of information (Labovic, 2011).

In the context of the Customs Administration, corruption has a specific role and impact. As an institution responsible for monitoring and regulating import-export processes, customs authorities are particularly exposed to corrupt practices that can undermine their legitimacy and effectiveness. For instance, customs officials may accept bribes to allow illegal imports or exports of goods, manipulate documents, or favour certain companies. Such practices result in direct economic damage to the state, as well as a weakening of the rule of law and legal certainty.

Moreover, corruption in customs has broader implications, as it affects economic stability, the competitiveness of domestic companies, and the international reputation of the state. At the same time, these corrupt practices create conditions conducive to organized crime, the trafficking of illegal goods, and even the financing of terrorist activities.

2.2 Corruption in the Customs Administration of the Republic of North Macedonia

National security is traditionally defined as a condition in which a state ensures the protection of its citizens, economic resources, and political institutions from threats that could disrupt social order, stability, and sovereignty (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime [UNODC], 2022). Contemporary threats to national security are no longer limited to conventional warfare or terrorist attacks but also include new forms of risk in which corruption and organized crime play a significant role.

Corruption in the customs administration of the Republic of North Macedonia represents a serious threat to national security for several reasons (CARM, 2015):

- **Weakening state control capacity:** When customs services are corrupt, illegal activities such as smuggling of weapons, drugs, counterfeit goods, and other illegal products may go undetected or be tacitly tolerated. This undermines the state's ability to control its borders and markets effectively.
- **Financing criminal groups and terrorism:** Corrupt channels facilitate the financing of organized crime and terrorist organizations, enabling them to sustain and expand their operations.
- **Undermining trust in institutions:** A widespread perception of corruption leads to a loss of public trust in government institutions and the judiciary, which may result in political instability and social unrest.
- **Creating an unfair competitive environment:** Companies that comply with the legal regulations are placed at a disadvantage compared to those that obtain privileges through corrupt practices.

According to reports from international organizations, corruption in customs represents one of the key risks to the security and economic development of the Republic of North Macedonia. Therefore, understanding this phenomenon and developing effective measures to combat it are essential for ensuring national security and long-term stability.

2.3 Institutional and Sociological Theories of Corruption

Corruption, as a social phenomenon, cannot be fully understood without analyzing the institutional and cultural factors that influence the behavior of individuals and organizations. Institutional theory, as proposed by Douglass North (1990), suggests that institutions –defined as formal and informal rules, laws, customs, and norms –shape the dynamics of social and economic relations. The quality and effectiveness of these institutions directly determine whether corruption is suppressed or allowed to flourish.

Klitgaard (1988), in his classical formulation of corruption, states:

“Corruption = Monopoly + Discretion – Transparency”

This formulation means that corruption thrives when officials have monopoly control over resources or services, possess discretionary decision-making power without sufficient oversight, and operate within a system lacking transparency and accountability. In customs services, where officials often exercise discretionary authority to approve or block the movement of goods, this combination creates conditions conducive to corrupt behavior. For individuals considering engagement in corrupt practices, the perceived cost includes both a moral component and the likelihood of punishment. Classical philosophical perspectives provide several guiding principles in this regard (Lukas & Rubel, 2004):

- Individuals should act consistently and in accordance with rational judgement.
- One should strive to maintain respect as a human being within society.
- Agreements with citizens should be honored in order to prevent social disorder, even in times of conflict.

A combination of high discretionary power – resulting in substantial potential gains from corruption – and insufficient accountability is widely regarded as one of the most common structural causes of corruption (Pei, 2009).

2.4 The Importance of Institutional Reforms

Effective efforts to combat corruption in customs require systemic institutional reforms, which include the following elements (Labović, 2022):

1. Systemic Rule of Law

- Establishing a systemic rule of law is a fundamental prerequisite for the development of the Republic of North Macedonia.
- The implementation of a comprehensive and unified system would accelerate economic growth, raise awareness among politicians and citizens, and significantly improve the Republic of North Macedonia's ranking on the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI).

2. Deep Structural Reforms

- Structural reforms are necessary within key systems and their subsystems to order to ensure qualitative, sustainable, and practically implementable changes.

3. Development of Public Awareness and a Critical Mass

- Citizens and experts, through engagement and public discussion, can create a critical mass capable of exerting pressure on political actors to pursue genuine reforms.
- Without informed and active citizens and experts, reforms cannot be implemented effectively or sustainably.

4. Expected Effects of Implementation

- Establishment of a functional and effective state.
- Significant improvement in the rule of law.
- Accelerated economic and societal development within a period of four to five years.

These reforms not only reduce opportunities for corruption but also strengthen public and business trust in the customs administration, which is essential for national security and economic development.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

To conduct a comprehensive analysis of corruption in the customs administration as a challenge to national security in the Republic of North Macedonia, this study employs a multidimensional research approach. This approach enables a systematic and in-depth understanding of the phenomenon, overcoming the limitations of traditional one-dimensional methods that focus solely on financial indicators or basic statistical data.

3.1 Approach and Methodology

The research is based on a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, aiming to provide a detailed and comprehensive analysis of corrupt practices, their consequences, and the effectiveness of measures implemented to combat them.

- **Qualitative approach:** This includes the analysis of relevant academic literature, official documents, strategic frameworks, and reports from national and international institutions (e.g., Transparency International, UNODC, and the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia). In addition, semi-structured interviews were conducted with security experts, customs officials, and representatives of NGOs engaged in anti-corruption initiatives.

- **Quantitative approach:** This involved the analysis of data on reported cases of corruption in the customs administration from 2019 to 2024, obtained from publicly available sources and institutional databases. This analysis covers statistical indicators such as the number of reported cases, their regional distribution, and the types of corrupt activities identified.

3.2 Multidimensional Approach – Balanced Scorecard

To overcome the limitations of traditional performance measurement based exclusively on financial results, this study applies a multidimensional approach grounded in the **Balanced Scorecard model** developed by Robert S. Kaplan and David P. Norton (1992).

This model translates the strategic objectives of the customs administration into specific organizational performance indicators, which are subsequently monitored, measured, and adjusted.

The Balanced Scorecard encompasses four key perspectives:

- **Financial perspective:** Analysis of financial losses resulting from corrupt practices.
- **Customer perspective:** Assessment of satisfaction among the business community and citizens with customs operations.
- **Internal processes:** Evaluation of the efficiency and transparency of customs procedures.
- **Learning and growth:** Assessment of institutional capacities and the ethical awareness of customs officials.

3.3 System Analysis and Indicator Weighting

The primary methodological tool used in this study is **system analysis**, which enables the identification of principles for constructing a list of **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** for the customs service in North Macedonia.

To determine the **relative importance** of each KPI (its weight), the **Weight of Metric** method is applied. The metric weight indicates the significance of a specific KPI in relation to other indicators within the hierarchical measurement system and is expressed as a **percentage share**. The cumulative value of all indicators equals **100%**.

Through the application of this methodology, targeted management and improvement of areas with the greatest impact on **combating corruption** and **strengthening national security** are made possible.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1: Reported Cases of Corruption in the Customs Administration of the Republic of North Macedonia (2019–2024)

Data up to September 2024

Year	Reported cases	Percentage change (%)
2019	120	-
2020	135	+12.5%
2021	110	-18.5%
2022	140	+27.3%
2023	130	-7.1%
2024	125	-3.8%

Source: State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption of the Republic of North Macedonia, 2019–2024

Analysis of Table 1: The table illustrates fluctuations in the number of reported cases of corruption within the Customs Administration of the Republic of North Macedonia during the period 2019–2024. The most significant increase was recorded in 2022, with a 27.3% rise compared to the previous year. This increase may indicate either improved efficiency in reporting mechanisms or an actual rise in corrupt activities. In contrast, the last two years show a slight decline in reported cases, which may be attributed to the initial implementation of anti-corruption measures.

Table 2: Main Causes of Corruption in the Customs Administration According to an Employee Survey (2023)

Cause	Percentage of responses
Low salaries	45%
Insufficient training	30%
Lack of transparency	60%
Political pressures	25%
Weak control mechanisms	55%

Source: Research conducted by the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of North Macedonia, 2023

Analysis of Table 2: The survey shows that most customs officers identify lack of transparency (60%) and weak control mechanisms (55%) as the primary challenges enabling corruption. Poor working conditions, particularly low salaries (45%) and insufficient training (30%), were cited as additional factors increasing the system’s vulnerability to corrupt influences.

From the data, it can be observed that reported cases of corruption in the customs administration show an overall upward trend with periodic fluctuations. The largest increase was recorded in 2019, coinciding with intensified control and anti-corruption measures by state institutions.

The growth in recent years may reflect improved awareness and reporting efficiency, but it may also indicate a deepening of corrupt practices, which poses a serious risk to national security.

Analysis 2: The Impact of Corruption in Customs on the National Security of the Republic of North Macedonia

Corruption in the customs administration is not only a legal or economic problem but also a serious challenge to national security. This phenomenon facilitates illegal activities such as smuggling of goods, trade in prohibited products, and the financing of organized crime, all of which directly threaten state stability.

One major consequence is the weakening of trust in state institutions. Citizens and businesses exposed to corrupt practices lose faith in the system, which results in reduced cooperation with competent authorities and diminished support for reforms. Additionally, corruption undermines economic security by increasing the shadow economy and reducing revenue from customs duties. This diminishes budgetary resources available for critical security and social programs, further elevating the risk of crime and social unrest. Data from oversight bodies and interviews with experts indicate that effectively reducing corruption in customs requires a systemic approach, including enhanced oversight, greater

transparency, and the education of customs officers on ethical standards and professional conduct.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS AND MEASURES TO STRENGTHEN SECURITY THROUGH ANTI-CORRUPTION PRACTICES IN CUSTOMS

- **Enhanced transparency and accountability**
One of the key measures is the introduction of systems that ensure full transparency in customs procedures. This can be achieved through the digitalization of processes, which reduces direct human intervention and the potential for corruption. Implementing systems that record and monitor all transactions and decisions allows for easier detection of irregularities and accountability of officers.
- **Training and education of customs officers**
Regular training on ethics, legislation, and the identification of corrupt practices is necessary to enhance awareness and professional capacity among customs employees. Through such training, officers will be better prepared to resist, report and prevent corrupt influences.
- **Collaboration with civil society and the media**
Active involvement of non-governmental organizations and the media in monitoring and investigating corruption creates additional pressure on authorities to comply with laws and ethical norms. The public must be informed and provided with mechanisms to report corrupt practices safely and anonymously.
- **Introduction of protection mechanisms for whistleblowers**
Protecting individuals who report corruption is crucial for the effective fight against corrupt practices. Legal and psychological protection, as well as guarantees of anonymity, are essential for encouraging whistleblowers without the fear of retaliation.
- **Institutional reforms and strengthened control**
Reforms in the institutional structure of customs, including the independence of anti-corruption bodies and the strengthening of internal controls, will allow for more effective detection, investigation and sanctioning of corruption.

6. CONCLUSION

Corruption in the customs administration represents a serious challenge to the national security of the Republic of North Macedonia. As an institution on the front line of protecting state borders and regulating imports and exports, customs plays a pivotal role in preventing criminal activities and safeguarding the economic sovereignty of the state. However, the presence of corrupt practices weakens this role and opens the door to illegal operations that threaten the economic system, security, and integrity of state institutions. Research indicates that corruption in customs undermines public trust in institutions, facilitates organized criminal networks, and reduces the effectiveness of efforts to combat crime and other illicit activities. Systemic weaknesses, lack of transparency, insufficient training, and weak control mechanisms create fertile ground for corruption.

From a national security perspective, this situation is alarming and requires urgent and comprehensive solutions. Implementing digital platforms and automated processes, enhancing the ethical capacity of officers through targeted training, and introducing

institutional reforms that enable independent oversight and whistleblower protection are key steps toward eradicating corruption.

Furthermore, involving civil society and the media as active partners in oversight and public accountability establishes a strong mechanism for preventing and sanctioning corrupt practices. Only through systemic, coordinated action by all relevant stakeholders can sustainably combat against corruption in the customs service be achieved, thereby strengthening the national security and institutional integrity of the Republic of North Macedonia.

7. REFERENCES

1. Customs Administration of the Republic of North Macedonia. (2023). *Annual Report on the Work of the Customs Administration for 2022*. Skopje: Customs Administration.
2. Kaplan, R. S., & Norton, D. P. (1992). *The Balanced Scorecard—Measures that Drive Performance*. Harvard Business Review.
3. Klitgaard, R. (1988). *Controlling Corruption*. University of California Press.
4. Labović, M. (2011). *Policing in Central and Eastern Europe – Social Control of Unconventional Deviance* [Conference proceedings]. Social Control of Institutional Organized Crime. <https://www.ncjrs.gov/pdffiles1/nij/Mesko/235122.pdf>
5. Labović, M. (2022). “Systemic Rule of Law Against Systemic Corruption and Organized Crime – New Epistemological Dimensions and Practical Consequences of Specific Proposed Solutions from the Strategic Vision for Deep Structural Reforms in Key Social Systems and Their Subsystems (2nd Edition)”
6. Lukas, G., & Rubel, W. (2004). *The Moral Foundations of Leadership*. Education, 116.
7. Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of North Macedonia. (2023). *Research on Factors of Corruption in the Public Sector*. Skopje: MIA.
8. Ministry of Justice of the Republic of North Macedonia. (2021). *National Strategy for Combating Corruption and Conflict of Interest (2021–2025)*. Skopje: Ministry of Justice.
9. North, D. C. (1990). *Institutions, Institutional Change and Economic Performance*. Cambridge University Press.
10. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2020). *Integrity in Customs: Taking Stock of Good Practices*. OECD Publishing.
11. Pei, M. (2009). *Government by Corruption*. Foreign Affairs, 26(1), 1–9.
12. Rose-Ackerman, S., & Palifka, B. J. (2016). *Corruption and Government: Causes, Consequences, and Reform* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
13. State Commission for Prevention of Corruption (SCPC). (2019–2024). *Reports on the State of Corruption*. Skopje: SCPC.
14. Transparency International. (2023). *Corruption Perceptions Index 2022*. <https://www.transparency.org>
15. United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC). (2022). *Corruption and Security: Threats to Development and Stability*. UNODC.